

Synthesis and Fungitoxicity of Some 5-Substituted-3-Polynitrophenyl Rhodanines

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Forty-four 5-substituted-3-polynitrophenyl rhodanines have been prepared by the condensation of reactive halogenonitrobenzenes and 5-substituted rhodanine in the presence of an alkali. They have been characterised and tested for their antifungal activity against *Helminthosporium sativum*, *Alternaria tenuis*, *Aspergillus niger* and *Fusarium oxysporum* by spore germination method. A relation between fungitoxicity and structure has also been established.

2-Mercapto-4-thiazolidones or rhodanines possess insecticidal and fungicidal properties¹. Recently

N-substituted-4-thiazolidones have been reported to possess anthelmintic², nematocidal³, pesticidal⁴ and fungicidal^{5,6} activity. Vander Kerk⁷ and Brown⁸ reported that 3-substituted aryl rhodanines are much more fungitoxic than the unsubstituted ones. A few 3-halogenonitrophenyl rhodanine were obtained by Gupta and Dureja⁹ by the condensation of halogenonitrobenzenes with 2-mercapto-4-thiazolidone, in ethanolic solution in the presence of potassium hydroxide. A study of literature reveals that only a few rhodanines with substituents present at position 5 have been studied. On the basis of these observations, it was thought of interest to prepare a large number of 5-substituted-polynitrophenyl rhodanines having halogen, nitro and methyl groups as substituents at different positions in the 3-phenyl ring, with a view to test their effect on fungitoxicity and to establish a relation between structure and activity.

5-Substituted-3-polynitrophenyl rhodanines(III) have been obtained by the condensation of halogenonitrobenzene(II) with 5-substituted rhodanine(I) in ethanolic solution in the presence of potassium hydroxide.

Thus sixteen halogenonitrobenzenes have been condensed with 5-substituted rhodanine to give the corresponding 5-substituted-3-polynitrophenyl rhodanines (Tables 1,2 and 3).

The I. R. Spectra of these compounds have also been recorded and are in complete agreement with their structures.

These compounds were tested for their antifungal activity against *Helminthosporium sativum*, *Alternaria*

tenuis, *Aspergillus niger* and *Fusarium oxysporum* by spore germination method⁹ (Tables 1, 2 and 3). The percentage inhibition of spores at 10 ppm have been recorded.

Experimental

*General method for the preparation of 5-substituted rhodanines*¹⁰ :

To a solution of 0.6 mole of aldehyde and 0.6 mole of rhodanine¹¹ in 400 c.c. of hot glacial acetic acid, 150 g. of fused sodium acetate was added and the mixture boiled for one and a half hour with occasional shaking. The substituted rhodanine soon separates out as orange yellow crystals. The whole mass was poured into 3 litres of water. The crystals that separated were filtered and washed well with water, followed by little alcohol and ether, yield 96% The product was recrystallised from acetone.

General method for the preparation of 5-substituted-3-polynitrophenyl rhodanines :

A solution of halogenonitrobenzene (0.01M) and potassium hydroxide (0.01M) in ethanol was added dropwise to a solution of 5-substituted rhodanine (0.01M) in ethanol (10 ml). The mixture was then refluxed for about four to five hours. On cooling the product was filtered, washed with water and crystallised out of acetone.

Rhodanines so obtained are insoluble in water and soluble in acetone. Their melting points, yield, analytical data and fungitoxicity have been recorded in Tables 1, 2 and 3.

Results and Discussion

5-Substituted-3-polynitrophenyl rhodanines have been found to possess marked fungitoxicity at 10 ppm level. Halogen and/or nitro group when placed at ortho and/or para position to the 3-phenyl linkage, enhances fungitoxicity to a greater extent. A halogen atom at meta position decreases the

TABLE 1—5-ANISAL-3-POLYNITROPHENYL RHODANINES

Sl. No.	R	M.P. °C	Yield %	Mol. Formula	%Nitrogen		%Sulphur		Percentage inhibition of spores at 10 ppm			
					Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.	HS	AT	AN	FO
1.	2,4-DNP	140	75	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₈ S ₂	9.85	10.07	15.10	15.34	28	30	25	28
2.	2,6-DNP	150	78	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₈ S ₂	9.82	10.07	15.05	15.34	32	32	30	35
3.	2,4,6-TNP	225	70	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ N ₃ O ₈ S ₂	11.90	12.12	13.62	13.85	40	50	33	38
4.	2-Chloro-4,6-DNP	195	80	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ N ₃ O ₈ ClS ₂	9.10	9.30	14.02	14.17	36	66	52	46
5.	2-Bromo-4,6-DNP	135	75	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ N ₃ O ₈ BrS ₂	8.26	8.47	12.62	12.90	20	18	22	6
6.	3-Chloro-4,6-DNP	155	80	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ N ₃ O ₈ ClS ₂	9.05	9.30	14.00	14.17	10	15	19	18
7.	4-Chloro-2,6-DNP	178	70	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ N ₃ O ₈ ClS ₂	9.08	9.30	13.96	14.17	15	19	25	15
8.	2-Methyl-4,6-DNP	130	78	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₈ S ₂	9.50	9.74	14.64	14.85	23	26	20	10
9.	3-Methyl-4,6-DNP	146	85	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₈ S ₂	9.45	9.74	14.62	14.85	28	31	22	18
10.	4-Methyl-2,6-DNP	99	65	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₈ S ₂	9.60	9.74	14.63	14.85	32	28	21	24
11.	3-Methyl-2,4,6-TNP	155	65	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₈ S ₂	11.51	11.76	13.23	13.44	24	25	28	20
12.	2,3-Dichloro-4,6-DNP	125	72	C ₁₇ H ₉ N ₃ O ₈ Cl ₂ S ₂	8.40	8.64	13.00	13.17	30	38	25	31
13.	2,5-Dichloro-4,6-DNP	75	70	C ₁₇ H ₉ N ₃ O ₈ Cl ₂ S ₂	8.38	8.64	12.95	13.17	35	38	23	33
14.	2-Chloro-5-methyl-4,6-DNP	80	70	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₈ ClS ₂	8.80	9.02	13.48	13.74	18	25	13	00
15.	2-Bromo-5-methyl-4,6-DNP	95	65	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₈ BrS ₂	8.48	8.23	12.32	12.55	15	18	10	5
16.	3-Chloro-2-methyl-4,6-DNP	148	68	C ₁₈ H ₁₂ N ₃ O ₈ ClS ₂	8.85	9.02	13.54	13.74	8	6	14	10

TABLE 2—5-BENZAL-3-POLYNITROPHENYL-RHODANINES

Sl. No.	R	M.P. °C	Yield %	Mol. Formula	%Nitrogen		%Sulphur		Percentage inhibition of spores at 10 ppm			
					Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.	HT	AT	AN	FO
1.	2,4-DNP	180	80	C ₁₆ H ₉ N ₃ O ₈ S ₂	10.65	10.85	16.25	16.53	22	20	25	10
2.	2,6-DNP	105	75	C ₁₆ H ₉ N ₃ O ₈ S ₂	10.68	10.85	16.30	16.53	28	25	23	12
3.	2,4,6-TNP	190	75	C ₁₆ H ₈ N ₃ O ₈ S ₂	12.65	12.96	14.60	14.81	35	28	30	10
4.	2-Chloro-4,6-DNP	80	82	C ₁₆ H ₈ N ₃ O ₈ ClS ₂	9.75	9.96	15.32	15.11	31	25	28	10
5.	2-Bromo-4,6-DNP	175	70	C ₁₆ H ₈ N ₃ O ₈ BrS ₂	8.85	9.01	13.52	13.73	25	15	20	00
6.	3-Chloro-4,6-DNP	85	78	C ₁₆ H ₈ N ₃ O ₈ ClS ₂	9.72	9.96	14.87	15.11	28	26	30	25
7.	4-Chloro-2,6-DNP	184	70	C ₁₆ H ₈ N ₃ O ₈ ClS ₂	9.68	9.96	14.90	15.11	30	30	32	20
8.	2-Methyl-4,6-DNP	178	80	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₈ S ₂	10.20	10.47	15.72	15.96	15	15	10	00
9.	3-Methyl-4,6-DNP	168	85	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₈ S ₂	10.22	10.47	15.80	15.96	30	26	16	28
10.	4-Methyl-2,6-DNP	170	65	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₈ S ₂	10.34	10.47	15.67	16.96	21	23	14	25
11.	3-Methyl-2,4,6-TNP	90	72	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ N ₃ O ₈ S ₂	12.24	12.55	14.07	14.35	18	20	23	8
12.	2,3-Dichloro-4,6-DNP	95	80	C ₁₆ H ₇ N ₃ O ₈ Cl ₂ S ₂	9.00	9.21	13.86	14.03	38	35	30	30
13.	2,5-Dichloro-4,6-DNP	145	80	C ₁₆ H ₇ N ₃ O ₈ Cl ₂ S ₂	10.18	10.47	15.67	15.96	31	30	35	35
14.	2-Chloro-5-methyl-4,6-DNP	92	85	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ N ₃ O ₈ ClS ₂	9.34	9.64	14.36	14.69	26	21	25	10
15.	2-Bromo-5-methyl-4,6-DNP	102	75	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ N ₃ O ₈ BrS ₂	8.50	8.75	13.04	13.33	16	10	15	00
16.	3-Chloro-2-methyl-4,6-DNP	176	70	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ N ₃ O ₈ ClS ₂	9.46	9.64	14.48	14.69	4	8	10	00

TABLE 3—5-PIPERONAL-3-POLYNITROPHENYL RHODANINES

Sl. No.	R	M.P. °C	Yield %	Mol. Formula	% Nitrogen		%Sulphur		Percentage inhibition of spores at 10 ppm			
					Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.	HS	AT	AN	FO
1.	2,4-DNP	195	80	C ₁₇ H ₉ N ₃ O ₈ S ₂	9.50	9.74	14.60	14.85	28	20	23	10
2.	2,6-DNP	220d	85	C ₁₇ H ₉ N ₃ O ₈ S ₂	9.47	9.74	14.56	14.85	31	33	26	16
3.	2,4,6-TNP	283	70	C ₁₇ H ₈ N ₃ O ₈ S ₂	11.50	11.76	13.16	13.44	36	50	15	18
4.	2-Chloro-4,6-DNP	220	60	C ₁₇ H ₈ N ₃ O ₈ ClS ₂	8.80	9.02	13.50	13.74	25	28	30	8
5.	2-Bromo-4,6-DNP	84	65	C ₁₇ H ₈ N ₃ O ₈ BrS ₂	8.06	8.23	12.78	12.55	15	20	18	4
6.	3-Chloro-4,6-DNP	185	80	C ₁₇ H ₈ N ₃ O ₈ ClS ₂	9.23	9.02	13.52	13.74	21	24	15	0
7.	4-Chloro-2,6-DNP	115d	76	C ₁₇ H ₈ N ₃ O ₈ ClS ₂	9.25	9.02	13.45	13.74	32	16	18	10
8.	2-Methyl-4,6-DNP	215d	80	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₈ S ₂	9.12	9.44	14.20	14.88	15	10	10	0
9.	4-Methyl-2,6-DNP	280d	65	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₈ S ₂	9.18	9.44	14.26	14.88	20	24	13	0
10.	2,3-Dichloro-4,6-DNP	235d	75	C ₁₇ H ₇ N ₃ O ₈ Cl ₂ S ₂	8.21	8.40	12.52	12.80	25	28	21	6
11.	2-Chloro-5-methyl-4,6-DNP	250d	80	C ₁₈ H ₁₀ N ₃ O ₈ ClS ₂	8.58	8.76	13.06	13.33	28	20	25	10
12.	3-Chloro-2-methyl-4,6-DNP	118d	75	C ₁₈ H ₁₀ N ₃ O ₈ ClS ₂	8.52	8.76	13.10	13.33	26	25	18	10

DNP and TNP refers to dinitrophenyl and trinitrophenyl respectively. All melting points are uncorrected. Satisfactory C, H analysis have been obtained for all these compounds.
 HS, AT, AN and FO refers to *Helminthosporium sativum*, *Alternaria tenuis*, *Aspergillus niger* and *Fusarium oxysporum* respectively.

fungitoxicity. A methyl group at ortho or meta position in 3-phenyl ring usually decreases fungitoxicity. However, at the para position, a methyl group enhances fungitoxicity.

Rhodanines carrying anisal group at position-5 are more fungitoxic in comparison to other rhodanines carrying piperonal or benzal group.

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